

DIDACTIC PROVISION OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PERSONAL QUALITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation

In higher education, the use of didactic tools in the training of future educators is organized by the teacher. Therefore, it is envisaged to use didactic tools in general secondary schools, and in vocational education and higher education institutions, to prepare and conduct lectures and practical exercises. For this, the curriculum and subject content are first thoroughly studied, and an electronic textbook or manual, virtual exhibitions, and didactic materials are prepared. This mainly involves presenting theoretical information, developing theoretical and technical thinking in students, arousing interest in the course content, and developing motivation for training in a specialty.

Keywords: Nature, child education, games, ecological awareness, pedagogy, nature study, creative activity, physical development

Preparing a lesson using didactic tools. When using a set of didactic tools in lessons, especially audiovisual tools, it is recommended to do so in the following order:

- a) preparing didactic tools for the lesson:
- b) preparing students to perceive the information of the didactic tool:
- g) a brief explanation by the teacher to demonstrate the materials contained in the didactic tool.
- d) organizing the consolidation of information in the didactic tool in the student's memory;
- j) giving homework to supplement the information contained in the didactic tool, etc.

Also, when preparing technical tools, audio, video tools for a lesson, they should be tested several times, and after consulting with a specialist, the equipment should be tested. After making sure of this, you can proceed to demonstrate the didactic tool.

Teachers' work in accordance with the following modern requirements in preparing didactic materials for training sessions creates the necessary conditions for achieving the expected educational result:

- be clearly goal-oriented;
 - be prepared in accordance with the needs and interests of students;
 - be based on educational information;
 - have the ability to activate;
 - create conditions for students to work actively in pairs and small groups;
 - develop independent, creative, critical and creative thinking skills in students;
 - have a modern significance;
 - be aesthetically high-quality;
 - be free from ambiguous concepts and expressions;
 - be able to guarantee a specific result;
 - be able to apply in various situations;
 - serve to strengthen existing knowledge, skills, and qualifications.
 - pay attention to the reliability of educational information when preparing didactic materials;
 - pay special attention to the formation of creative thinking skills in students and create an atmosphere of creativity between teachers and students in the teaching process;
 - creative approaches to creating curricula and educational resources, creating tasks related to the intellectual development of students.
 - take into account the ideological, scientific, visual, systematic, consistent presentation of educational information, and the interrelationship between educational information in the effective formation of didactic educational materials;
- Didactic support for the development of professional personal qualities of future educators is the organization of a special methodological and educational process for the formation of knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for their future professional activities. This process is formed on the basis of didactic principles of education and includes the following aspects:
- The main goal of didactic support is to prepare future educators for professional activity. In their professional activities, the educator must not only master the curriculum, but also develop the personal and professional qualities necessary for working with children.
- The main tasks of didactic support for the development of professional and personal qualities of future educators are:
- Formation of professional knowledge and skills.
 - Development of communication skills.

- Increasing psychological stability and pedagogical skills in working with children.
- Development of empathy, kindness and patience in educators.

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